

Investigating the Outcomes of Organisational Restructuring: A Case Study of Oman's Public Sector

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Abstract:- The Omani authorities started to implement Oman vision 2040 after the new era. The government began reorganising and structuring several ministries as a reflection of the new cost reduction policies and resisting global financial catastrophe. The research shows the outcomes of the Omani organisation restructuring in their departments, the relationship between corporate restructuring and employees satisfaction, and the Omani government workers' perception of the current governmental restricting. The research provides a recent reaction to this restructuring and fills the gap of the absence of data and information on the consequences of the Omani governmental reorganisation. Quantitative data is used to analyse through an online questionnaire as a research instrument with the help of secondary data to show the outcomes of this restructuring. The sample is taken from one of the restructured departments; non-probability sampling is used with the help of the judgmental sampling technique. The research reveals weak Omani media coverage of the plans for the restructuring, the increase in early retirement among The Omani public sector workers, management conflicts inside the merged departments, and the decrease in the number of new employments in the Omani public sector and the remain of the traditional formal management style after the renewal of the government structure

Keywords:- Restructuring, Change Management, Autocratic, Governmental Reorganising, Employee Satisfaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Background of the Research

The constant changes in the external environment are massive, making government and managements take other directions and new methods to keep moving without unexpected failure. The majority struggles to underline the essence of change as a part of life individually in society and with groups in the working fields. These changes create a big gap between those who practice avoiding the outcomes and still believe sticking with their old methods is the central pillar. Organisational restructuring is a part of a significant mechanism governments use to keep reducing environmental pressure, reorganising plans, and saving resources as possible (Mano & Rosenberg, 2014). In Profitable organisations and companies, the reason to switch and reorganise the structure of the firms is to dodge workforce challenges, face competitors' improvements, answering stakeholders' demands which are complex in those organisations are large (Bowman et al. 1999). It's obvious to recall the difference

between profitable organisations and non-profitable organisations in the shape of leadership, types of services, and directions. However, the consequences of change vary between the consideration of the governmental laws, actual administration inside organisations, their listed plans, and the reaction of their employees and people who get those services. According to Cico et al. (2021), restructuring enables the government to overcome the economic crisis and enforce power to control under those circumstances. Governments restructure to increase efficiency, improve productivity, reduce public spending and renew programs that aim to cut costs in numerous ways (Gonas, 1994). In the case of the Sultanate of Oman, vision 2040 is clear that the future will complexly change the look of the public sector and its contribution to society. Sultan Haitham bin Tariq, the ruler of Oman, declared 28 royal decrees which targeted to merge 10 ministries, remove five councils and announce more restructuring and changes that will target governmental ministries in the future to face economic downturn and achieve the goals of Omani Vision 2040 (Al Balushi, 2020). Nevertheless, governmental restructuring hits bigger scales and reaches multiple firms, departments, courts, and institutes which regenerate enormous impact within that geographical region. The transformation from planning to implementing this vision by the government allows this research to have an open field to examine the consequences of those actors upon employee satisfaction, work productivity, and turnover actions considering the lack of such information yet to be available for Omani and foreign reviews to have access.

The introductory paragraph outlines clearly the objectives and motivation for writing the paper.

B. Statement of the Research Problem

The problem with public sectors is that they are closed environments that lack transparency, clarity and freedom. However, those reasons are understandable if we deal with multiple countries with different regimes; they are not performing the same. The public sector focuses on serving the public, obtaining order, and setting regulations inside the country. Organisational change is different in public sectors, which are implemented in a strict, formal environment that lacks the participation of employees in decision-making. Moreover, Employee involvement is missing in the Omani public sector. There are rare research that address their opinion and issues conducting organisational restructuring inside their environment and how they absorb these significant changes. Employee satisfaction is critical and affects the organisation, while the workforce is an exciting factor that can change the look and atmosphere inside those

targeted firms. The research will address the missing chain of how organisational restructuring ignores some of the reactions and negative aspects of these changes in motivating their workers. Many research papers address the impacts and outcomes of corporate restructuring concerning cost reduction, organisational performance, and financial reasons. However, this research will analyse how these impacts affect workers inside a formal organisation. The nature of Omani citizens or employees is calm and respectful to their parents, supervisors, and directors. These deeds are taken from respecting the country's traditions and religious teaching. However, international employees can be bolder and stricter regarding their rights, and it is easier for them to change some of the systems and rules they are forced to deal with, even in the public sector. The research understands this issue, like Omani employees can be a future threat if every employee will not stick to what they believe and know their right to be involved in the change that associates their presence inside organisations, whether in the public or the private sector.

C. Aim

The research aims to explore the outcomes of organisational restructuring implemented in Oman's public sector, the relationship between employees' engagement, satisfaction towards corporate reorganisation, and the employee's opinions and perceptions of this new environmental change in their life and the organisation itself

D. Research Objectives

- To investigate the outcomes of organisational restructuring in Oman's public sector.
- To examine the relationship between organisational restructuring and employee satisfaction.
- To evaluate the issues of organisational restructuring in Oman public sectors.
- To analyse the employee perception of organisational restructuring in Oman's public sector.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Organisational Restructuring

The concept of organisational restructuring has been revealed precisely by multiple scholars. According to Bansal (2021), organisational restructuring is the adaptation of new behaviours and different ideas and the modification of people, technology, and structural alterations. Adapting change is an act that happens after the restructuring, which can target the firm's surroundings. Organisational restructuring is a systematic reconstruction and modification of the firms operating rules and structure (Borowiecki, 2014). The main changes happened to the system, which is the organisation's base and regulations which control the internal environment and define how organisations interact with the external environment inside the country or worldwide. According to Mckinley & Scherer (2000), there are three types of restructuring that occur in firms: organisational, financial, and portfolio. These changes are different from each other and do not precisely happen all at once in a particular organisation. In addition, the organisational focus of the

hierarchy and structure while financial restructuring can also be a cause for the restructuring discussed under another subtitle. Organisational restructuring is a complex process that leads to significant change that aims to shape current and long-term attributes that target internal needs and evolve the internal environment (Szuster, 2020). However, this definition addresses successful organisations that pay attention from the beginning to the needs of their workers and environment to prevent adverse shocks on the outcomes of those changes. Organisational restructuring is a massive change in assist composition and corporate strategy (Heugens & Schenk, 2004). Many authors believe that restructuring changes plans, fund generation and the nature of work. However, Governmental restructuring could be shallow and create change on the surface to have the impression of a vast restructuring. According to Yui & Gregory (2018), Governmental restructuring action defines as the transfer of functions between firms and the change of organisational names. It's not apparent yet if those shallow restructuring acts are government responsibility or external forces pushing the government to apply weak actions toward improving their governmental organisations to cope with the changes happening in work. In addition, definitions of restructuring is still a big concept to search for, especially on what platform and country will implement those changes. A country can apply a restructuring idea and have a blurred vision of how these restructures will end up in the future.

➤ The Causes of Organisational Restructuring

According to Yin et al. (2022), corporate restructuring caused by managers found a lack of productivity improvements, weak business performance, an undeveloped economy, and high-cost production. These acts force the management of corporations to adapt fast and create new plans to coup with these reasons. Poorly organised firms are always motivated by market pressure to change their organisations (Brickley & Drunen, 1990). In some circumstances, weak corporations accept change due to the strong demand of competitors and the negative external environment. In addition, these changes are done by outside forces, which are toxic. Operation performance is the leading cause of organisation restructuring due to its essence and mindset to change the whole firm based on how the corporation gains and produces effective performance to meet its goals. According to Kang and Shivdasani (1997), 92 Japanese companies experienced organisational restructuring due to their decline in corporate performance. Government restructuring cause is to focus on social service delivery and less efficient, while other governments use privatisation restructuring provisions (Warner & Hebdon, 2001). Some governments can't compete with private sector companies in efficiency and productivity. In addition, some governments restructure and switch their operations to privatisation roads to enhance their social services and lower society's frustration with some of the services which lack proficiency. However, it is unfair to compare both sectors for the causes of the restructuring, and they have different effects on the environment. The government is pressured to obtain social and political concerns inside and outside the country. According to Hyderabad (2014), the causes of organisational restructuring are (1) the change in the legal environment, (2)

the emergence of new technology, (3) poor valuation, (4) refocusing strategies, and (5) Competitive pressure. However, the government is responsible for setting the laws and regulations in all fields, which will never make it an issue if they adjust some rules to fit their views. On the other hand, the main concern is if those regulations are meant to be positive and support the internal environment, including employee engagement and satisfaction. Governmental restructuring is caused by the increased burden of long-term obligations towards the organisation's subordinates and the employment process (Hyderabad, 2014).

➤ *The process of organisational restructuring*

The process of organisational restructuring

Fig 1: The process of organisational restructuring (Kowalski, 2021)

The actions taken during corporate restructuring does vary from organisation to another. Scholars show that many firms use various methods in their restructuring process, which contains different steps. Managers with high skills attempt to realise the steps required to fix the issues that corporations suffer from and translate them into an action plan. According to the Institute of Company Secretaries of India (2014), the corporate restructuring process must ensure those aspects are considered while implementing organisational restructuring, which are: (1) legal and procedural issues, (2) competition aspects, (3) taxation aspects, (4) Accounting aspects, (5) cultural synergies. These pre-steps are essential and make managers confident enough to start operating their restructuring processes in the organisation, which uncertainty about the external environment precisely may cause unknown outcomes. There are ten steps which differentiate corporations between success and failure in conducting restructuring; they are (1) legal framework, (2) securing the liquidity facility, (3) restoring market confidence, (4) assurance of government, (5) approval of restructuring plan, (6) identification of assets, (7) conclusion of agreements, (8) effective collection and payment of the debt, (9) update to all stakeholders, (10) avoid patchwork (Ashby, 2015). According to Kowalski (2021), Large corporations use 4 phases to implement organisational restructuring: planning phase, implementation test phase, measurement phase and full rollout. The planning phase is understanding the needs of the internal aspects of the organisation, from communication to achieving team support and selecting suitable managers who understand the goals and are creative. The implementation phase is a test for a small-scale of one country to understand the environment and avoid risks and costly mistakes. The measurement phase is essential to monitor the process; the restructuring will be useful and risky if the testing is false. In the full rollout phase, the companies apply corrections to the implementation and measure the final results.

➤ *The outcomes of organisational restructuring*

Fig 2: Model of the Antecedents and outcomes of corporate restructuring (Johnson, 1996)

Organisational restructuring is an action which centre a force of change and consequences. Every action reacts to life, considering physics. However, those outcomes are controlled by pre-reason, which is why the organisation agrees to the wind of change. According to Johnson (1996), antecedent conditions lead organisations to restructure, including changes in environmental conditions, ineffective strategies, firm governance, poor performance and financial restructuring. In addition, Johnsons explained that those antecedents are a crucial factor in why corporations adopt restructuring, and the outcomes will affect the firm's strategy, performance and employee performance. Previous scholars identified multiple outcomes from different journal papers what restructuring outcomes are in those points in the path of firm strategy and performance: (1) restructuring cause a decline in performance, reduced employment and the engagement of assets sale, (2) improvements in operation performance cause of asset sales, (3) investors reacts negatively to the layoff announcements and poor performance, (4) divestment had a positive effect on firm performance, (5) managers selling assets to generate short term profits (Johnson, 1996). According to Strelnik (2015), corporate restructuring can be used as a risk treatment method in which restructuring implementation reduces organisations' risks and results in changing corporation structure, portfolio, finance and assets. This restructuring method generates better outcomes dealing with external environmental threats that the company isn't expecting, which is helpful for long-term organisational stability.

B. *The relationship between organisational restructuring and employee satisfaction*

➤ *Employee Satisfaction*

The essence of employees for organisations is enormous. Employees are the core of firms and their workforce. They are the base that more the organisation forward and the focus that managers tend to work with to achieve the goals and purposes of those organisations. According to Tanković et al. (2022), managers are responsible for creating an environment in which employees love to work to boost organisational performance. However, the concept of employee satisfaction is mentioned in various scholarly papers and different from one another, which are the reason for where those employees are from, their culture,

and the rules and regulations. Employee satisfaction is the indicator and a representation of workers' positive and negative feelings toward their work (Dayal & Verma, 2021). According to Feleke et al. (2021), employee satisfaction is pleasant emotion that results from the assessment of work for every employee. The satisfaction factor came from employees finding a job more enjoyable, independent, and having training. Satisfied workers reduce the lethal internal environment inside the organisation, allow managers to cooperate more with staff, enhance employees' contribution to management decision-making, and create healthy competition between the subordinates. Employee satisfaction is an overall feeling about the work and related attitudes about various aspects of the work itself (Mahmoud et al., 2022). Feleki et al. (2021) acclaim that there are three critical factors for employee satisfaction which are : (1) the business must be guided by treating employees fairly, and human values, (2) the behaviour of workers will affect the organisation operations, (3) employee satisfaction can be an indicator for the firm's activities. Still, fair treatment varies from one part of the world to another, including the country's regime, regulations, and labour laws. In addition, the situation in government is more concerning if these governments are not applying international laws that multiple countries have agreed in the U.N. and other organisations. Employee satisfaction might differ in developed countries with international laws and respect for employees. In contrast, some countries are restricted with unhealthy, strict and formal regulations that are less interested in what their employees suggest or think about the working environment, making it harder to identify clearly.

➤ *The relation between employee satisfaction & corporate restructuring*

The act of restructuring is an internal tool and affects those inside that field, from humans to objects. Managers might have a slight advantage and fewer effects after organisational restructuring, whether they ordered those changes or came from a higher authority. According to Howard & Frink (1996), restructuring influences changes in motivation, internal work and employee satisfaction. The age of employees plays a role in employee satisfaction while corporate restructuring is implemented (Rhodes, 1983). Older employees resist more change than newbie employees because they used to do the job for more than 25 years straight. When those restructures happened, senior employees struggled more than senior managerial employees (Howard & Frink, 1996). This research indicates differences in how experienced employees work. They have a bigger chance of retiring and leaving the organisation if managers' opinions are not listened to. New employees will accept or forced to take charge more because they need the job anyways. According to Howard & Frink (1996), organisational restructuring influence the nature of interactions inside the work more without influencing the firm's tasks. Employees are humans who interact and communicate inside the firm; therefore, the relationship is intense and affects them directly on how they take the new job, understand the tasks, communicate with their colleagues and their relationships with the managers and supervisors. Managers must inform their employees of the significance of restructuring and how these modifications

opened opportunities for them and built-up growth (Hackman & Oldham, 1980). Managers are responsible for finding common ground when restructuring happens to prevent employees from being shocked about massive changes that can increase their uncertainty. According to El Din & El Ghetany (2016), employee satisfaction increases while restructuring the firm if those changes are close to their values and national culture. Employee satisfaction and restructuring are not affected by gender, level of education and experience inside the organisation but have a huge impact and change with the age of employees. These answers from previous scholars show that the differences can be shocking from one country to another, which gives the research more opportunity to reveal the relationship between Oman employees after implementing the governmental restructuring to compare with those researchers and how Omanis reaction is to the wind of change in the economy.

➤ *Government restructuring*

According to Stone (2002), The government must lead and establish proprieties and limit social and economic costs in corporate restructuring. However, how will the government deal with their restructuring and based on which criteria? Most researchers address corporate restructuring done in big business organisations and companies and local governance restructuring. The government restructure their facilities to adopt commercial approaches more than service operations (Harris & McGrady, 1999). The financial crisis in 2008 and 2014 was one of the reasons many governments started to adopt restructuring and look from the economic perspective towards their operations, not mentioning yet the environmental factors such as the Covid-19 pandemic, which is another case that has its effect on government restructuring. In addition, the government's primary goal is to cope with global changes and reduce public service costs. Soulsby & Clark (2013) claim that senior managers have political roles in governmental restructuring using forms of power, domination of law and formal ways of management. The government appraises these managers to set the rules correctly and apply that restructuring implementation smoothly from the government's point of view. However, this aggression and action are not acceptable in many countries, and it causes concerns with human rights organisations. In addition, the force the government are planning to use to set the rules could create a hostile relationship like the organisation that has been restructured and the connection between those senior managers and the subordinated unhealthy. According to Samboteng et al. (2022), governments intend to use restructuring to accelerate the bureaucratic process to create a small but functional government. Nevertheless, these bureaucratic processes, which are services to the public, are more noticeable while the implementation of the governmental restructuring due to fixed works, new jobs being created, and employees changing their positions based on the recent reorganisation. Governments practice formal management style and restructuring force to protect their resources from unexpected threats, which sometimes lacks planning and reinventing processes (Wald, 1999). However, the government has the power to plan, design, and set these rules as they claim for the benefit of the people. Governmental restructuring differs from companies'

corporate restructuring for demographic and social reasons. However, eternal players are always particular governments to go with the flow and be their organisations modernised with their rules and manners

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

➤ *Research Design*

Fig 3 Research Design

Successful research is meant to be required a suitable research methodology design and shape. Researchers attend to choose the proper plan and path before collecting data and analysing it through the design of the research methodology. Research design is an overall plan that connects the problems and provides specific directions for the procedure in research (Creswell, 2014). According to Kerlinger (1984), the research design is a structure and strategy adopted in the investigation of the study to obtain the answers to research questions with the presents of variables. However, suppose there's no research design. In that case, the researcher will be lost in a giant field of information and hesitates to choose the proper analysis tools to make the research reliable and genuine. The readers will find it hard to collect the findings when the data has been analysed.

A quantitative research design will be used in the research, which will suit this study type. According to Kothari (2007), quantitative research is a measurement and technique that produce calculated values and is suitable for close-ended responses. The research will depend on primary data that is essential in the research and secondary data that will be collected from various websites and journal articles from sites like MEC library and Masadar. The research will conduct in a non-experimental design type which is not related to discovering new variables in the research. The main variables of the research are already available and present: organisational restructuring that happened in the firm and employee satisfaction which is present in one way or another. Survey research will be used in this study and contains a preparation of 100% close-ended questions and will be sent to the subordinate as an online survey. According to Asenahabi (2019), the survey method is the collection of data from a sample group to determine the status of this particulate group in that actual time concerning more than a single variable. Reaching subordinates to pass the survey will be affordable for the researcher. If physical copies are not reached, online documents will be sent by e-mail to them and shared through social media platforms as an easy way to spread and access the survey to those subordinates. This method will prevent wasting time, lower the cost of transportation to reach those employees, and make conducting surveys easier for associates in the office or their homes.

➤ *Population*

	Research target	Population	Sample	Expected respondents
Explanation	Restructured Oman Public sector ministries	Recently restructured ministry	Human resources department	Employees, retired employees
Number	26 ministries	1	250 employees	50 employees

Table 1 Population

People are a source and the core of any business or organisation. The population is those people who the researcher in focused scope targets. According to Casteel & Bridier (2021), population contains two parts, the population of interest and the target population. The research will be interested in Oman's public sector as the main population that the investigation will analyse and extract the data from those employees working inside this population. However, the research will only target the restructured public sector ministries and wait for the employee's responses from that population target. The Sultanate of Oman severely changed the government apparatus by restructuring and merging 26 ministries, reducing the number to 19 ministries. Therefore, the research will choose one recently restructured ministry that experienced this renewal process in the mid of the year 2022 as its targeted population. The study will focus on the human resources department. Choosing a recent fresh example of restructuring is essential to the reader and the researcher to analyse and experience how the public sector has not been in the spotlight for scholars locally, and it's a new event that requires understanding, studying, and looking for the results. Since Omani restructured the public sector, the population differs from the restructuring of the private sector

in Oman or outside in the shape of restructuring, the cause, and the consequences. The research respects the type of regulations and the laws of the Sultanate of Oman on the privacy and confidentiality of this sector. Therefore, the study is aligned with those regulations to prevent mentioning the ministry name that has been chosen as the population. However, the results will be shown, which contain transparency and will give a general look at the consequences of this restructuring based on this Population

Fig 4 Sample Size and technique

The population is comprehensive and contains lots of players and diversity. The huge number of people makes academic scholars' life harder when conducting research. Therefore, taking a small amount of this population is essential and makes it easier for the researchers to start collecting the data. The sample of the population in this

research will be taken from a selected human resource department inside one of Oman's public sector ministries that implemented an organisational restructuring recently. The reason for choosing this particular research is the target of a researcher because most employees are experienced with the ministry workforce, and their needs are aligned with the research that wants to understand the employee's perception of organisational restructuring. The department is divided into three buildings, with one director and multiple managers. However, the researcher will target only regular employees and administrative. The total number of employees in the human resources department is 250 employees. In addition, the expected respondents of the sample are listed as 50 employees in one of those buildings located in Muscat, Sultanate of Oman.

Non-probability sampling is used to explore, and trail research and not everyone in the population can participate in the represented sample (Ayhan, 2011). The analysis uses non-probability sampling to avoid the participation of the managers and directions who had participated in the making of the organisational restricting in this ministry. The research will use the judgment (purposive) sampling technique method as a base to start picking the respondents. The judgmental sampling technique is used when the researcher chooses his participants by his judgment while keeping the purpose of the study, planned to address a specific plan in the researcher's mind, and is less costly. According to Wisniowski et al. (2020), non-probability sampling has limitations that lack mathematical theories that result in measurement and accuracy uncertainty. However, the research is focused on the employees' reaction and view on an experience and inner senses that do not include scientific and math equations.

IV. STATISTICS AND DATA ANALYSIS

The outcomes of organisational restructuring Organisational restructuring, cost reduction and efficiency.

Organisational restructuring helps management to reduce costs and increase efficiency. 31 responses

Fig 5: organisational restructuring cost reduction and efficiency

Financial performance is essential in private and public sectors, which is the base of their contribution to the people and community. Even the public sector has been critically affected by global financial problems during multiple crises in the last decades. Restructuring is a method to boost the organisation financially. Managers have adopted the restructuring of organisations to illustrate better performance,

improve employee welfare and increase productivity (Lal et al. 2001). According to Kwaning et al. (2014), organisational restructuring is an act that helps organisations ion to make it more profitable, revise their strategies, and adjust their financial plans. The previous literature and scholars show that the outcomes of organisational restructuring are aligned with boosting management efficiency and adaptiveness to compete with a challenging business. Yet, the government is affected by the financial crisis and the contribution of the private sector in the country. The burden will be more significant if the public sector is only responsible for generating profit for the country. According to the responses to the questionnaire, approximately 80% of the respondents agreed that organisational restructuring helps managers and executives in upper positions in the government to reduce costs and provide better efficiency. 48.4% agree about the statement, and 29% strongly agree, while only one responder disagrees.

➤ *The forms and faces of the organisational restructuring*

What forms of organizational restructuring happened to your organisation? 31 responses

Fig 6: the forms and faces of corporate restructuring

The form of organisational restructuring may change from one management to another on their reason for particular restructuring. Indeed, the restructuring has various faces and colours to adapt. Figure 6 shows the employee's opinions about the actual form of organisational restructuring conducted in their department. 54.8% of employees think that the primary outcome of the restructuring was merging their organisation departments into smaller numbers and containing fewer managers. On the other hand, about 20% of the respondents think retirement was a significant outcome of organisational restructuring in their firm. In addition, the government's intention to decrease the number of Omani public sector employees was the third choice for about 13%. According to Breinegaard et al. (2017), organisational change and poor psychosocial work environment is associated with non-disability early retirement in public service employees. Job withdrawal significantly rose among employees after restructuring, which was a reason for the management to downsize the firm, which increased employees' will to leave the firm in the shape of retirement of turnover (Probst, 2003). According to Dzwigol (2019), restructuring is a natural consequence of managing enterprises which include merging and lower number of departments and management to restore an internal balance inside firms.

➤ *The issues of organisational restructuring*

What are the issues of organisational restructuring at your workplace?
31 responses

Fig 7 : the issues of organisational restructuring

The employee's participation in the question was diverse and contained three central answers on the issues raised after their department was restructured. The main result of restructuring was affecting their motivation. 32.3% of the total respondents believe that the new restructuring and rules will reduce incentives in the organisation. The second issue the employees raises is feeling uncertain about their future in the firm after restructuring with 25.8% votes. The third issue of restructuring in employees' eyes where the slow change that happened during the restructuring. Some employees still don't know to which department they will transfer, and others still don't have available offices. According to Varma (2017), the organisation's challenges to creating a motivated enrolment are the ignorance of employee motivation, lack of management commitment towards employee expectations, weak competitive organisation structure and policies, and a narrow managers mindset. The mentioned organisational restructuring type is an imposed corporate restructuring in the Omani public sector. Imposed organisational change is made from a position of power and implemented solely by the upper leaders, making it hard to negotiate and fix (Rodat, 2018). Employee uncertainty is the most challenging aspect of organisational change. Not understanding the difference could affect their opportunities, training requirements and if they still have their succulent job after the restructuring (Bordia et al. 2003).

➤ *Organisational restructuring & employee satisfaction*

There is a relationship between organisational restructuring and employee satisfaction.
31 responses

Fig 8 : organisational restructuring & employee satisfaction

The employees' responses to this question show that they find a connection between their motives and satisfaction that can be affected after organisational restructuring. The respondents' answers show that more than 60% of the employees agree that restructuring can affect their motivation, work in the firm, ambition and competition inside the workplace. However, 22.6% are unsure if restructuring is a severe issue against their dreams and motivation. During organisational change, the vision of the leaders, role modelling, encouraging group identity and collaborations affect employee satisfaction (Albion & Gagliardi, 2007). Non-profitable organisations focus on similar restructuring factors like profitable firms such as portfolio and finance in response to the changing enjoyment. These changes and tasks influence employees directly and where they are located in the new system, impacting their internal work and motivation (Howard & Frink, 1996). In addition, the previous researchers discovered that for organisational restructuring to be less toxic towards employee satisfaction, the management should consider boosting opportunities to balance the relationship between corporate restructuring and employee satisfaction and make workers stay and continue their hard work.

➤ *Employee knowledge about the restructuring*

Oman's public sector needs to be restructured.
31 responses

Fig 9 : the Omani public sector restructuring needs

The Omani public sector employees recently experienced the restructuring and agree that the sector needs change. According to figure 4.12, the calculations show that 71% of the respondents agree that the industry needs to be renewed. However, employees expected these changes to be beneficial and positively impact their presence and future in the workplace. The intention of the employees to change was dominant in their answer and shows that they look for a better lot and hope this restructuring will affect their work career to the best. However, the new reorganisation and work regulations will allow new public sector employees to occupy temporary contracts rather than permanent contracts to increase competitiveness in the public sector (Times of Oman, 2022). This move has a negative aspect on employees' stability socially and financially.

The government explained to the media why the public sector needs to be restructured.
30 responses

Fig 10: organisational restructuring & the Omani media

The responses show the employee's uncertainty whether they have been told in the media in detail about the importance of Oman's government restructuring, the outcomes and their future. The numbers show that 50% of the employees knew about restructuring motives and details, while the other half were confused and never knew about those aspects and the government's intentions and plans. Media is essential in life nowadays and plays a role in transforming information and data fast. With the transformation of technology and social media, governments should reach the mass of people through that advanced technology to present their work even in a formally regulated country. Deane (2015) states that media and communication are essential to governance. They should invest in media to build independent media sectors, increase transparency, enhance government accountability to citizens, and support democratic decision-making mindsets.

➤ *Employees and the motive of restructuring the Omani Government*

Why is the Omani public sector restructuring?
31 responses

Fig 11: employee perception of the Omani corporate restructuring

Understanding employees' perceptions and views on the government's motives are critical to the research. Employees are, in the end, average citizens. They react to their external surrounding and news, whether true or false. The calculations in figure 11 illustrate the employee's opinions about the Omani government's motives to restructure the public sector. The most chosen reason was the financial crisis that hit the globe, regionally and specifically Oman in 2008 and 2014. About 32.3% of the respondents think the financial crisis damaged the economy and affected the Omani GDP. The second pick was to adjust new rules and regulations the government has already implemented to cope with the change. Finally, political reasons were another choice by the

employees, which is unknown and hidden due to the nature of the government and public sector not showing specific information for security purposes. According to Peterson (2017), Job opportunities in the public sector for young Omanis are shrinking because of the financial crisis and low oil prices. According to Al roya (2015). The ministry of finance intends to stop promotion for employees in the Omani public sector due to the drop in oil prices and to reduce spending. According to Charoenseang & Manakit (2002), restructuring the financial system and improving corporate governance are solutions to defeat the financial crisis.

V. DISCUSSION

The data has been analysed, and the employee's responses were handy in concluding the research with the upcoming information that was useful. The Omani public sector's employees participate in this research to point out the outcomes of the Omani government restructuring while they are working in one of the governmental facilities, the relationship between employee satisfaction and this particular restructuring, the issues of this organisational restructuring and the employee's perception of the corporate reorganisation. The content of this chapter will reveal the summary of findings based on the four objectives of the research, a conclusion of the data analysis, the research recommendations to the management, employees and ordinary readers of the investigation, the limitations of this research and the upcoming future research. The study will briefly review the Omani public sector feel and deal with current times. This research will fill a gap in the absence of mentioning such a perception of this current governmental movement in employees' eyes with transparency and honesty.

VI. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

A. The outcomes of The Omani Governmental restructuring

The Omani government planned to restructure their facilities from the last decade through Oman Vision 2040 and their government officials through the media. The research finds out that the outcomes of the Omani governate restructuring outcomes are the following:

➤ *Merging Ministries And Cancellation Of Some Omani Government Facilities*

The research examined the employee's responses that most of their departments were blended to a smaller number and combined their employees under more prominent offices. In the chosen department, 3 offices are separated with three central managers, which shrunk the department to 2 and cancelled one management position. According to the media, multiple ministries were cancelled and incorporated in 2020 to follow the government's plan.

➤ *Reduce Spending And Cost Reduction*

According to the Omani government, the motive behind the restructuring is to cope with the current financial position and look differently at the country's resources. Oil prices affected the government's visions, so they planned to cut some spending and restructure the government to eliminate

unnecessary expenditures that would not affect the citizens. The government succeeded in reducing the losses resulting from resources and gave them more time to think of other alternative solutions to overcome the issues.

➤ *Decrease New Employment In The Public Sector*

Restructuring is a downsizing procedure that affects the corporate shape. The size of the organisations will allow new employees to participate and have a massive desire for citizens to employ in one of the governmental departments that will create job insurance for them. Employment in the public sector decreased compared with previous years to the government's vision and well to open another working environment in the private sector and manufacturing for Omanis to work there. Restructuring affected employment, and the number of new workers decreased.

➤ *The Increase In Retirement Among Omani Government Employees*

During the restructuring planning and before implementation, some of the senior employees decided to retire early. Other employees who did not compete for 20 years in the workplace also applied for early retirement. The retirement took place before, during and after restructuring. The employees chosen to complete the questionnaire confirm this by pointing out that a considerable number of senior employees retire without knowing what the restructuring will bring to the table and its shape.

B. The relationship between organisation restructuring and employee satisfaction

The study shows a strong bond between employee satisfaction and restructuring on how the organisation will be stable internally and contains a healthy working environment. The employees agree that their motivation and satisfaction with working in a good environment that respects their views and protects their future is a priority. However, many restructuring programmes and plans ignore employees' motives because the main reason is to regulate new rules to reduce financial problems and issues in the private sector.

C. The issues of the Omani governmental restructuring

There are multiple issues recorded and discovered from the employee's responses and the secondary data because of the Omani government restructuring; there are the following:

➤ *Employee Uncertainty*

Multiple concerns from the perspective of employees in this research illustrate their fear and overthinking of how this restructuring will affect their future. Employee uncertainty about whether the Omani public sector will still cover their ambitions and life insurance. Most of the responses pointed out that this issue is still not solved and the government is defending their moves as necessary to overcome external threats.

➤ *Formal Leadership*

Before restructuring, the Omani public sector management was formal, traditional and strict. After the restructuring, some of the managers did not change their

attitude and maintained the same leadership style, creating more division between employees and them after the restructuring. Some managers lack the skills to contain their staff during a crisis and other dramatic changes, making employees more confused and scared about the new reorganisation and situation.

➤ *Lack of Collaboration Between Merging Offices*

The study examines less cooperation and teamwork between new employees coming to their department due to the restructuring; some of the Omani ministries suffer from this eternal issue in the implementation of the reorganisation and afterwards. Some managers refuse to collab with the new employees, and others clash with their visions and plans, while ministries merging contains a big gap for the newly restructured ministry to move forward and complete their goals. In addition, some of the moving employees did not have any offices available after moving to new departments, and some managers did not still know their new employees yet, which shows that the restructuring process was unplanned and slow.

➤ *Absence Of Media To Present The Omani Government Restructuring*

Citizens lack essential information about the government's move to change their visions and structure. The government showed their Oman vision 2040 plan to the media and the internet, which details. However, that information is not easy to analyse by a regular citizen and a simple employee. There was minimum information for the Omani restructuring while researching for secondary data in English, which is concerning.

D. Employee perception about the Omani government restructuring:

The Omani employees are willing to work on any condition available; The study shows that the intention to work in different situations was not an issue for the workers. They think they are better suited to the new position after restructuring, which shows the nature of the Omani worker that has good social interactions and adaptation to change. However, their perception of the apparent purpose of restructuring was missing due to the lack of media telling the restructuring details of the management practices that did not change after the restructuring. Employees admit that there are not against any restructuring from the Omani government unless it will not affect their income and social insurance.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

Sultan Haitham bin Tariq had his unique thoughts and visions to continue the renaissance but on a different path with different external challenges and threats that affected the Sultanate of Oman. The Omani governmental restructuring had positive and negative outcomes, which are understandable due to their limited experience in adjusting to a new system. Many Omanis are still appraising their life during Sultan Qaboos's rule and did not adapt to new methods and changes. The government did a good job reducing the effect of the financial crisis and the decreasing prices of oil to

diversify their resources and cut down spending, one of the main reasons for the Government restructuring to cut the government spending which success. However, challenges raised with this restructuring on how the internal working environment of the Omani public sector will still have its glow of insurance and protection to its employees if they have to find other safe and profitable jobs.

RECOMMENDATIONS

After analysing the Omani governmental restructuring and its effect on Omani employees, the research will recommend multiple solutions, and simple points which researchers and executives benefit from oncoming restructuring events or similar plans to this research will be issued in points in the following lines:

A. Transparent & detailed restructuring plans in the Omani media

The research suggests the government be more specific in showing the methods of their work that will affect the citizens and Omani workers with transparency, the reasons for the restructuring, social insurance, who will be involved in the restructuring and the duration of it. This information can be presented on government television, radio and social media to attract more views and citizens with different backgrounds. The transparency between the government and the citizens creates a strong bond and a healthy environment to accept changes.

B. Flexible leadership styles

The government should focus on changing the mentality of senior leaders and managers in some ministries, which still have a strict and old mentality that clashes with the governmental intentions to renew their shape and restructure. After restructuring, some managers have formal and autocratic management styles, which is toxic to most employees in the public sector. Young managers with flexible leadership styles that could switch between democratic, lassies-fair style are helpful to reduce the pressure on the government toward the insistence of some employees that refuse the environment after restructuring.

C. Profitable Government departments & practices

The Omani government, after restructuring, should make every department of their government profitable and attracts income. The plan is similar to privatisation, but the government will gain from it, increasing its profits by giving raises, increasing employee salaries and opening new employment. Some departments can be financially independent of this plan, similar to the experience of Muscat Municipality and the Royal Police of Oman. The offices can invest inside the country to open institutes, buildings, and malls, which will need people to run and more employees to hire. Investing in research and development is another factor to open the views more on this point and make it profitably easier with different practices depending on the department and the ministry.

D. Involve employee satisfaction in upcoming governmental restructuring

Employees are essential to the organisation. Their behaviour is vital in the firm. Involving employees in the decision-making of the reorganisation will prevent any adverse reactions in the post-restructuring phase. These acts will help employees build confidence and collaboration with government which will create healthy future leaders aligned with the government's views and goals. Upcoming restructuring should balance the importance of profit, finance and human resource.

E. Create a healthy competitive business market for turnover and career transition

The Omani government is focusing on shrinking the public sector and reducing employment. The research recommends the government invest in other sectors like manufacturing, marketing, tourism and green economy to attract new employees. The government should make those other sectors profitable and equal to the public sector so the pressure will be less on the government. For Example, in Japan nowadays, the government is looking for foreign workers to participate in the logistics sector due to the lack of Japanese workers, with most of them operating in the manufacturing sector. The Omani government should attract investors to boost this idea without restrictions and rules similar to Dubai. Suppose the Omani worker found out these other sectors are more profitable. In that case, the pressure on the public sector will be minimal, and it will help new employees switch their minds and ideas to the new reality more quickly.

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